

INTERVIEW	How long have you worked in game development?	What is your age range?	What are you currently studying?	Have you already informed yourself about the LGPD related to data protection?	Have you ever taken a course focused on privacy or specific data protection?	Are you working at the moment?	If you have ever worked at a company, approximately how many employees worked there?	What platform or technology have you developed games for?	What roles/functions have you performed when developing games?	How many years of experience do you have in software development, excluding games? On what platform(s)?
Interview 1	9 years	31 to 35 years old	Doctoral candidat	Partially	No	Yes	20	Unity, GameMaker, Construct	Programmer, game designer, level designer	4 years in web and desktop platforms. PHP and Python languages.
Interview 2	2 years	18 to 25 years old	Undergraduate student	No	No	No	I didn't work in a company	VR mobile, web e PC (linux e windows).	Developer and Game Designer	1 year in swing applications for computers in java.
Interview 3	5 years	18 to 25 years old	Undergraduate student	Yes	No	Yes	6	Computers, cell phones and Oculus Quest 2.	Programmer, Programming Lead and Company Founder	7 years Mobile, web and desktop. C#, Java, python and C.
Interview 4	I have been participating in competitions and gaming groups for almost 3 years	18 to 25 years old	Undergraduate student	Partially	No	Yes		I have developed games in Unity and Pygame for the Itch.io web platform during game competitions and personal projects.	Programmer and Game/Level Designer	I participated for 2 years in research and scientific initiation projects related to software development.
Interview 5	4 years	26 to 30 years old	Doctoral candidat	Yes	No	Yes	6	I have developed VR and computer games.	Programmer and Designer	Adding up all the time worked, it's 4 years. In all of them I worked using Unity and Construct3.
Interview 6	3 years	31 to 35 years old	Master's candidate	Yes	No	Yes	40	Construct, Game maker, Unity, Unreal Engine	Lead Designer and Senior Programmer	5 years in: C#, C++, HTML Android and Windows
Interview 7	6 years	31 to 35 years old	Master's candidate	Partially	No	Yes	12	PC (Windows, Linux e Mac) Mobile (Android e iOS) Consoles (Xbox e Nintendo Switch) Webmobile (HTML5)	Programming Leader	12 years Web backend (Java and C#) Web frontend (Html, css,)
Interview 8	7 years	41 to 45 years old	Doctoral candidat	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	Unity (mobile, PC, VR)	Game Designer, Game Tester	web devices